

**Functional Medicine: Rooting Optimum Outcomes for Health
and Uprooting Illness**

**Alternative Therapies involving Functional Medicine Lifestyle statistic data for Healthcare
Professionals**

Post- Doctoral Research PhD 2020-2021

Dr. David Render DNH PhD candidate

Pages 3

Functional Medicine: Rooting Optimum Outcomes for Health and Uprooting Illness

Functional Medicine operates in an atmosphere scope on the how and why illness happens individually and in a social or national setting. Figuring out the root positioning will restore health of the disease the person is suffering from.

Understanding individual lifestyle is important of dietary eating and individual and family history notes that is patient or client centered. Science –based approach that bring forward truths of life to patient power. There are underlying causes of dis-ease giving way to optimal wellness. Effective processes come by understanding factors of data genetic, biochemical, and lifestyle and direct personalized treatment plans for improved patient outcomes.

Rooting up the source of illness. Become oriented to simplify and going from there. Functional Medicine treatment targets specific manifestations of disease.

The Institute of Functional Medicine survey findings in a clinical setting below insights:

- Almost all Functional Medicine will give recommendations of supplemental vitamins and minerals to their patients.
 - Over 70% percent of first time is longer visits of 60 to 120 minutes versus average care primary visit 15- 20 mins or less than that.
 - Evidence based healthcare gives way to knowledge plus skills
 - 43% physicians practicing Functional Medicine in their 70s, regarding greater work job satisfaction.
-

Functional Medicine, Nutrition, Health and Wellness, Health Statistics, Education, Social Health,
Conventional and Integrative

Reference

Institute for Functional Medicine, <https://www.ifm.org/learning-center/introduction-to-functional-nutrition/>

FUNCTIONAL MEDICINE IN PRACTICE

Business and Practice Models for the Functional Medicine Clinician <https://www.ifm.org/functional-medicine/functional-medicine-in-practice/>